

Appendix E.1 - Taxonomy Development Process

Identify problem and motivate: The targeted user groups were identified as academics and practitioners, for which the taxonomy aims to facilitate coherent scholarly and practitioner dialogue.

Define objectives of taxonomy: Meta-characteristic defined as *definitional features that differentiate the objects.*

Objective Ending Conditions (Nickerson et al., 2013)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All objects have been examined 2. At least one object is classified under every characteristic of every dimension. 3. Every dimension is unique and not repeated in the taxonomy 4. Every characteristic is unique within its dimension. <p><i>We excluded the mutual exclusivity condition, as taxonomies containing business model objects are frequently characterized by overlapping attributes (Möller et al., 2022). We also excluded the merging or splitting condition, as the objects were to be classified in their original form.</i></p>
Subjective Ending Conditions (Nickerson et al., 2013), Mais & Bauernhansl (2024)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concise: The number of dimensions allow the taxonomy to be meaningful without being overwhelming 2. Robust: The dimensions and characteristics sufficiently allow for differentiations to be made between the objects 3. Comprehensive: All objects of interest are able to be classified by the taxonomy 4. Extendible: New dimensions or characteristics can be added 5. Explanatory: The taxonomy helps to explain the similarities and differences between the objects
Evaluation Goals (Kundisch et al., 2022)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identification: The taxonomy dimensions and characteristics serve as search criteria to facilitate the identification of the objects 2. Classification: The taxonomy classifies the objects based on their differentiating features, thereby contributing to their clarification

Design and development: Design and development was informed by the demonstration and evaluation rounds. The ending conditions and evaluation goals' assessment by participants over the sessions is provided in the table below.

Type	Ending conditions	Iter.1	Iter.2	Iter.3	Iter.4
Objective	All objects have been examined	X	X	X	X
	At least one object is classified under every characteristic of every dimension.	X	X	X	X
	Every dimension is unique and not repeated in the taxonomy.		X		X
	Every characteristic is unique within its dimension.		X	X	X
Subjective	Concise: The number of dimensions allow the taxonomy to be meaningful without being overwhelming.	X	X	X	X
	Robust: The dimensions and characteristics sufficiently allow for differentiations to be made between the objects.		X		X
	Comprehensive: All objects of interest are able to be classified by the taxonomy.	X	X	X	X
	Extendible: New dimensions or characteristics can be added.		X	X	X
	Explanatory: The taxonomy helps to explain the similarities and differences between the objects.			X	X

Evaluation Goals				
Identification: The taxonomy dimensions and characteristics serve as search criteria to facilitate the identification of the objects.	-	-	X	X
Classification: The taxonomy classifies the objects based on their differentiating features, thereby contributing to their clarification.	-	-	X	X

Demonstration and evaluation: The demonstration and evaluation session design details per Szopinski et al. (2019) are shown in the table below. The rater protocol provided to participants can be found in the second document attached to this online appendix.

Who (subject of evaluation)	<i>Involvement in taxonomy building</i>	Subjects have not been involved in taxonomy building
	<i>Background</i>	Academics
	<i>Experience</i>	Domain and Method
What (objects of evaluation)	<i>Type</i>	About real-world
	<i>Involvement in taxonomy building</i>	Objects have been used in taxonomy building
	<i>Coverage</i>	Representative
How (method of evaluation)	<i>Approach</i>	Mixed-methods
	<i>Method</i>	Focus group

Communication: The taxonomy is presented in our paper.

Appendix E.2 - Rater Protocol for Taxonomy Demonstration & Evaluation Session 3

Contents:

- Section 1: Demographic questions
- Section 2: Sustainability-Oriented Business Model Concept Definitions
- Section 3: Sustainability-Oriented Business Model Concept Taxonomy
- Section 4: Evaluation Goals Questionnaire

Section 1: Demographic questions

Name:	
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Participants will be anonymized.

Section 2: Sustainability-Oriented Business Model Concept Definitions

Concept	Definition
Sustainable Business Models	<p>A Sustainable Business Model (SBM) is a business model that creates, delivers, and captures value while explicitly integrating economic, environmental, and social sustainability goals into its core operations and stakeholder relationships [1]. SBMs represent a comprehensive reconfiguration of business logic where sustainability is not an add-on but a core design principle that reshapes how value is defined, created, and distributed by the business [2, 3]. SBMs are sometimes also referred to as Sustainability-Oriented Business Models or Green Business Models, where the former label is used interchangeably with SBM by some authors [4, 5], and the latter label tends to be used in policy-related contexts [6].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The primary goal of an SBM is to contribute to sustainable development by generating integrated economic, environmental, and social value, aligning with the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) principle of sustainability [7]. SBMs aim not only to maintain firm profitability but also to reduce negative impacts and increase positive outcomes for society and the natural environment, often seeking to create value beyond organizational boundaries, including for communities, ecosystems, and future generations [8].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> SBMs operationalize their goals by embedding sustainability principles into their value proposition, internal processes, and stakeholder governance. Key mechanisms include aligning and managing diverse stakeholder interests, integrating environmental and social factors into strategic decision-making, and applying a system-level perspective that considers the firm’s broader social-ecological context [5, 9, 10]. SBMs adopt a long-term perspective and promote stakeholder stewardship in both environmental and social responsibility.</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> SBMs are supported by sustainable innovations and organizational tools, including technological and social innovations, new business architectures and models (e.g., product–service systems, bottom-of-the-pyramid models), performance measurement systems based on TBL sustainability metrics, and collaborative value networks that span public, private, and nonprofit actors [11–13]. These enablers help firms implement, monitor, and adapt their sustainability logic across complex, multi-actor business ecosystems.</p>

<p>Circular Business Models</p>	<p>A Circular Business Model (CBM) is a business model that creates and captures economic value through loop-based resource strategies that slow, narrow, and close material and product flows [14], thereby contributing to circular economy (CE) transitions. CBMs are thus business model implementations that operationalize principles of the CE paradigm [15].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The primary goals of a CBM are to improve resource efficiency, reduce negative environmental impact, and align business practice with circular economy goals [7, 16]. CBMs can also aim to contribute to social impact creation, but the social dimension of sustainability is not intrinsic to CBMs and its realization depends on the CBM's design [17].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> CBMs function by applying circular principles such as reduce, reuse, recycle, remanufacture, refurbish, extend product life, and dematerialization [18, 19]. These mechanisms enable firms to recirculate parts and materials, minimize input needs, and design products and systems that slow, narrow, or close resource loops. Coordination among stakeholders and a long-term orientation [20, 21] are critical to making these mechanisms work.</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> CBMs are supported by specific technologies, materials, and organizational tools, including product–service systems (PSS), sharing platforms, reverse logistics, remanufacturing/refurbishment capabilities, product design for circularity, closed-loop supply chains, digital technologies, and recycled materials [9, 15]. These enablers facilitate the implementation and scaling of circular strategies across the value chain.</p>
<p>Circular Economy</p>	<p>The Circular Economy (CE) is a macro-level economic system paradigm [22, 23] that aims to minimize waste and emissions, optimize resource use, and enable sustainable development by intentionally designing out linearity and maintaining the value of resources in circulation for as long as possible [24]. It is a systemic transition framework that guides public policy, industrial ecosystems, and cross-organizational value creation towards long-term resource resilience and efficiency [25].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The CE aims to primarily achieve environmental and economic sustainability by replacing the incumbent linear take-make-waste model [16, 17] with systems that extend resource lifecycles, reduce pollution, and decouple economic prosperity from environmental degradation [21]. It often serves as a strategic response to resource scarcity, climate pressure, and the need for system-wide sustainability transitions [26].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> The CE operates by embedding circular strategies across production–consumption systems that aim to slow, narrow, and close resource loops. These include reuse, repair, remanufacturing, recycling, recovery, and product life extension [23, 24, 27]. Other mechanisms include shared stakeholder responsibility [23], durable product design [28], and maintenance-driven value preservation.</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> CE implementation is supported by enablers such as closed-loop infrastructure, regenerative and restorative product design, digitalization, reverse logistics, renewable energy use, and cross-sector stakeholder collaboration [17, 24, 28]. These enablers provide the structural capacity to scale circular mechanisms across sectors and geographies.</p>
<p>Product-Service-System</p>	<p>A Product-Service System (PSS) is a value delivery mechanism or strategy wherein firms combine tangible products with intangible services in their offering to provide utility without necessarily transferring product ownership [12, 29]. It thus functions as an implementation logic that supports the goals of broader business model frameworks.</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The primary goal of PSS is to enhance resource efficiency and reduce environmental impact by extending product lifecycles, lowering material throughput, and decoupling value creation from material consumption [16]. PSS tend to focus on economic and environmental outcomes [12]. Social value creation is not a core goal of PSS but can be integrated if deliberately pursued in the firm's broader business model [29].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> PSS operates by replacing or augmenting the sale of products with service-based offerings such as maintenance, leasing, usage contracts, or performance guarantees. PSS variants include product-oriented PSS (product plus services), use-oriented PSS (access without ownership), and result-oriented PSS (payment based on achieved outcomes) [30, 31]. These mechanisms slow material loops, extend product lifespans, and promote more sustainable resource consumption patterns.</p>

	<p><i>Enablers:</i> PSS can be supported by product-service offering value propositions, reverse logistics, digital platforms, intelligent monitoring systems, and closed-loop infrastructure that enable resource usage tracking, service fulfilment, and circular performance delivery [16, 30]. These enablers allow firms to coordinate value creation across the full product lifecycle and support the operationalization of sustainability goals.</p>
<p>Sustainable Business Model Innovation</p>	<p>Sustainable Business Model Innovation (SBMI) refers to the process through which firms innovate or transform their business models to integrate sustainability as a central component of value creation, delivery, and capture [32, 33]. It reflects a shift from traditional economic-centered models toward those that embed environmental and social considerations at the core of business logic, thereby enabling organizations to pursue long-term viability that balances economic, environmental and social impact [34].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The primary goal of SBMI is to create significant positive and/or significantly reduced negative impacts on the environment and society [34]. It supports broader sustainability goals by integrating sustainable value creation into the business model, aiming for balanced economic, environmental, and social outcomes [35]. SBMI is aligned with the ambition of achieving sustainable development and addressing stakeholder expectations related to sustainability [5, 36].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> SBMI operates predominantly by changing existing value propositions in how value is created, delivered, and captured, towards models that promote shared and sustainable value [32, 37]. This includes designing and implementing new (sustainable) business models, making novel and non-trivial adjustments to key elements or the overall architecture of existing business models, and integrating sustainability concerns into core business strategy, operations, and decision-making [36]. Another central mechanism involves the proactive inclusion and management of stakeholders to ensure that business models are responsive to the needs and expectations of customers, communities, suppliers, the environment and society [32].</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> SBMI is enabled by both structural and leadership-related drivers. These include innovation types such as business model transformation, diversification, the acquisition of sustainable models, and the development of sustainable start-ups [32]. Additionally, it is facilitated by managers who act as sustainability leaders within organizations by championing new mindsets and guiding the transition toward business models rooted in sustainable principles [36].</p>
<p>Circular Business Model Innovation</p>	<p>Circular Business Model Innovation (CBMI) refers to the process through which organizations redesign or develop business models to align with circular economy principles, with the objective of transitioning from linear to circular configurations of value creation, delivery, and capture [18, 38]. CBMI is distinguished by its focus on extending resource utility, minimizing negative environmental impact, and fostering closed-loop systems through systemic innovation in business architecture [39].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> Organizations engaging in CBMI aim to advance their environmental sustainability by aligning business models with circular economy principles. This involves minimizing their waste, emissions, and pollution, while simultaneously maximizing the retained value of products, components, and materials over time. The ambition is to decouple economic activity from resource depletion by slowing and closing material loops and promoting regenerative practices.</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> The CBMI process can take four forms according to Geissdoerfer et al. [24]: the creation of circular start-ups, diversification into circular business models, the acquisition of existing circular business models, and the transformation of current business models into circular ones. These activities are supported by the deliberate, non-trivial reconfiguration of firm's value creation, delivery and capture mechanisms to reflect circular economy logics and priorities.</p>
<p>Eco-Innovation</p>	<p>Eco-Innovation (EI) is a type of innovation and refers to the production, assimilation, or exploitation of products, production processes, services, or management and business methods that are novel to the organization and explicitly aimed at mitigating environmental burdens, optimizing resource efficiency, and enhancing sustainability performance [40, 41]. EI is conceptualized as both a means to reduce the environmental impacts associated with production and consumption, and as</p>

	<p>a strategic mechanism to facilitate an organization's transition towards circular business models [42].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> EI aims to address the environmental impacts arising from the production and distribution of goods and services by minimizing resource consumption, reducing waste generation, and lowering the environmental burden relative to the value of outputs [40, 43]. EI also seeks to contribute to sustainable development by promoting resource efficiency, mitigating pollution, and supporting the systemic shift towards the circular economy wherein environmental and economic benefits are pursued in parallel [42].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> EI is operationalized through both technological and non-technological innovations that enable more efficient use of natural resources and reduce the environmental impacts of production methods [41, 42]. This encompasses the introduction or modification of products, services, processes, or organizational practices that are novel to the firm and explicitly designed to enhance environmental performance.</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> The implementation of EI is facilitated by the development of new or improved products, production processes, services, and management or business methods, as well as system-level enablers such as organizational and process innovations [42]. The use and measurement of eco-efficiency, an indicator defined by the ratio of added product or service value to environmental impact, serves as a tool to measure environmental performance improvements [43], thereby guiding innovation efforts towards the achievement of sustainability targets.</p>
<p>Sharing Economy</p>	<p>The Sharing Economy (SE) refers to an economic model centered on the temporary access and shared use of underutilized resources, enabled through collaborative interactions that are mediated by digital platforms [44–46]. It represents the transition away from traditional ownership-based consumption toward economic models that prioritize access, collaboration, and the intensified use of assets [45]. The concept is grounded in both social and environmental aims, distinguishing itself from conventional market systems by promoting new patterns of consumption and value distribution [43].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The Sharing Economy primarily aims to intensify the use of otherwise underutilized assets thereby facilitating product reuse and product lifetime extension, contributing to sustainability objectives and sustainable development [43, 47]. Social impact is also central to SE, as it encompasses goals such as equal access to goods and services, the empowerment of consumers and communities, and the facilitation of new and flexible forms of employment [45]. These goals reflect a value system that privileges access over ownership and encourages inclusive, collaborative participation in economic activity.</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> The Sharing Economy functions through temporary, access-based business models and digital marketplaces that connect consumers directly (C2C) to share goods and services [47, 48]. These mechanisms rely on network effects, accessibility-driven peer-to-peer exchanges, and the recirculation and intensified use of goods and services [43, 48]. By leveraging digital technologies to mediate exchanges, sharing practices enhance resource efficiency and minimize the need for individual ownership of infrequently used products. The mechanisms thus support collaborative consumption and enable the reconfiguration of how value is generated and distributed within marketplaces [45].</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> The Sharing Economy is enabled by collaborative online platforms that facilitate temporary access to goods and services by connecting users and coordinating exchanges [5, 43, 48]. These platforms act as intermediaries that support the functioning of access-based and collaborative consumption models, providing the digital infrastructure necessary for matching supply with demand and enabling peer-to-peer transactions.</p>
<p>Sharing Economy Business Model</p>	<p>A Sharing Economy Business Model (SEBM) is a business model that facilitates access to goods and services through collaborative consumption, rather than individual ownership [46]. SEBMs operate by leveraging underutilized resources, reshaping customers' consumption patterns, and fostering new value creation pathways that are central to both economic and social exchanges in the SE [44]. Various types of SEBMs can exist depending on the economic context in which they operate. The various</p>

	<p>economic contexts include access-based economies, community-based economies, platform economies, peer-to-peer (P2P) economies, and second-hand economies, each of which reflect diverse value creation logics within the broader SE landscape [26, 44].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The primary goal of an SEBM is to create sustainable value by promoting the efficient use of underutilized resources, avoiding overconsumption, changing consumer habits, and fostering social connection between consumers [44]. SEBMs thereby contribute to sustainability by reducing environmental load, enhancing social well-being, and generating economic benefits. Their provision of access to products and services as an alternative to ownership further supports new consumption patterns that emphasize use over possession [26].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> SEBMs achieve their goals by facilitating collaborative consumption, which entails the sharing, renting, swapping, pooling, and lending of resources [44, 46]. This mechanism enables consumers to access goods and services through various forms of shared use, reducing the need for individual ownership and supporting more sustainable consumption patterns.</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> SEBMs are supported by value propositions that merge the principles of the second-hand economy, on-demand economy, and service-oriented logic [26]. This integrated value proposition allows SEBMs to scale, adapt to diverse market contexts, and effectively meet consumer needs within the framework of shared resource use. In some cases, SEBMs can make use of technological platforms which facilitate transactions, coordination, and trust among users [44].</p>
Hybrid Organizations	<p>Hybrid Organizations (HOs) are organizational forms that operate at the intersection of multiple institutional domains [49, 50], combining traditionally distinct practices, elements and objectives from the public, private, and nonprofit sectors within a unified business model [51, 52] to address sustainability-related challenges through innovative, boundary-spanning approaches.</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The central goal of HOs is to address sustainable development challenges by generating integrated forms of value that respond to both societal and market needs [50–52]. This involves generating integrated economic, environmental, and social value. They also aim to generate value for both shareholders and the business community [51], demonstrating their dual orientation toward both mission and market imperatives.</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> HOs achieve their goals by combining market-based approaches with mission-oriented practices [52], and by engaging in hybrid entrepreneurship that blends institutional expectations from multiple sectors, enabling them to simultaneously pursue profit and purpose. HOs realize their goals by navigating and managing conflicting institutional and mission logics which arise due to the varying institutional fields and sustainability dimensions they bridge [49].</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> HOs are enabled by innovations that challenge the status quo and allow for the reconceptualization of conventional business practices and approaches [50].</p>
Social Enterprise	<p>A Social Enterprise (SocEnt) refers to a hybrid organizational form that integrates a primary social mission into the business to achieve social and economic sustainability [51, 53]. These organizations are established with the deliberate intent to address societal challenges through entrepreneurial means, while maintaining financial viability. Generated profit is typically reinvested into the enterprise to further its social mission [53]. Social enterprises are also referred to as hybrid enterprises, and span the boundaries of public, private, and non-profit sectors to generate dual forms of value [49]. A normatively defined subtype of Social Enterprises is the Social Business, which are non-dividend based, and in which all profits are reinvested into the same company or other social businesses to maximize social outcomes [54].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The principal goal of a social enterprise is to pursue a dual mission entailing the creation of measurable social value alongside the attainment of economic profit [51, 55]. This dual mission is referred to as a double-bottom-line, and broadly forms the defining feature of Social Enterprises, including for the Social Business subtype.</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> Social enterprises realize their double-bottom-line mission by using business models that integrate social objectives directly into the processes of value creation, delivery, and capture while maintaining economic viability [53]. These models are supported by social entrepreneurship, which emphasizes the agency,</p>

	<p>innovation and experimentation process required to challenge conventional business norms and to mobilize diverse resources across sectoral boundaries [54]. In the Social Business subtype, traditional shareholders are replaced with mission-aligned stakeholders which serve to institutionalize social priorities within the organization's ownership and control structures and maintaining accountability for the dual mission [26, 54].</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> An enabler in Social Enterprises is the presence of value propositions that translate social impact into financially viable outcomes, allowing them to sustain operations while delivering social value [5]. Social business models may serve as a structural template for Social Enterprises to embed stakeholder-oriented governance, constrain profit distribution and formalize the reinvestment of profits, thereby maintaining the centrality of the dual mission in the enterprise's strategy.</p>
<p>Servitization-Based Business Models</p>	<p>Servitization-based Business Models (ServBM) are business models in which service offerings are sold based on products' use or performance, rather than complete product ownership[5, 22, 48]. The value-in-use of products is offered to customers; a shift that reflects a broader change in how value can be created, delivered and captured, placing more emphasis on services and outcomes than on product transactions.</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The main aim of ServBMs is to create added value by combining products with services that improve customer experience and long-term satisfaction [22]. Consequently, they can support the circular economy transition and bring environmental benefits, namely by minimizing waste and the consumption of virgin resources given their focus products' value-in-use [48, 56].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> ServBMs function by featuring value propositions in which product functionality is offered instead of offering product ownership, thereby providing access to the product's use instead of selling it. Some approaches include pure servicizing, where only usage of the product is offered, and hybrid servicizing, where both product ownership and usage are part of the offer [48].</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> To support this shift, ServBMs rely on product take-back, repair, and recycling systems, which help close resource loops and reduce environmental impact [56]. Another enabler is the use of pay-per-use pricing models [57], which allow customers to pay based on how much they use a product.</p>
<p>Sustainable Entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Sustainable Entrepreneurship (SusEntr) is an entrepreneurial approach that integrates the creation of economic opportunities with the explicit aim of addressing sustainability challenges [51, 58, 59]. It is grounded in the pursuit of both business innovation and the resolution of societal and environmental problems, positioning entrepreneurship as a key mechanism for advancing sustainable development and meeting the needs of broader society and stakeholders [58].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The primary goal of SusEntr is to contribute to solving sustainability challenges by addressing societal and environmental problems through entrepreneurial activity. Sustainable entrepreneurs aim to generate positive societal and environmental outcomes alongside economic value, ensuring that business success aligns with the broader interests of society and stakeholders [58].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> Sustainable entrepreneurs operationalize their goals through the development and realization of sustainability innovations [58]. Key mechanisms include the exploration and exploitation of sustainability-related market opportunities [59], and ensuring efficient production and use of resources [51], thereby leading to innovative (sustainable) business models. Through these mechanisms, sustainable entrepreneurs convert problems into opportunities, replacing unsustainable forms of production and consumption, and fostering effective projects and undertakings that contribute to sustainability outcomes [51].</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> Sustainable Entrepreneurs are enabled by various forms of sustainable entrepreneurship, including ecopreneurship, social entrepreneurship, and institutional entrepreneurship [58]. These entrepreneurial forms differ in the extents of their sustainability dimension orientations, relevant resources, and required institutional frameworks to initiate, support, and scale sustainability-driven ventures. They offer distinct yet complementary pathways for integrating sustainability into entrepreneurial processes and can be utilized in combination or isolation, depending on the sustainability mission.</p>

<p>Benefit Corporation</p>	<p>Benefit Corporations (B Corps) are organizations that obtain a formal certification or label awarded to for-profit companies that successfully meet rigorous standards of social and environmental performance, public transparency, and legal accountability [49]. This certification, granted through B Lab's third-party audit and associated legislation, signals an organization's verified commitment to balancing profit and purpose and contributing to sustainable development [52]. As such, Certified B Corps represent a subset of hybrid organizations [52] that legitimize and institutionalize the pursuit of sustainability objectives within their core operations, governance, and value proposition through a clear, transparent, and standardized certification process.</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The main goal of a B Corp is to pursue sustainability objectives that contribute to sustainable development while explicitly balancing profit and purpose [54]. This dual focus involves meeting and satisfying the needs of shareholders and stakeholders, including the environment and society, ensuring that organizational success generates positive outcomes beyond financial returns [52, 60].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> Adherence to the B Corp standards and audits' acts as the mechanism through which B Corps achieve their goal of integrating sustainability into core business operations, which encompasses environmental performance, public transparency, and legal accountability [49, 52, 54]. Additionally, corporate social responsibility (CSR) commitment embeds the purpose of serving the common good into the core of the business [49]. B Corps also strengthen stakeholder relationships by educating, raising awareness, and empowering consumers to adopt sustainable lifestyles and behaviors, thereby extending their sustainability impact beyond conventional market transactions [52].</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> The B Lab third-party audit and its rigorous certification standards and associated legislation enables the operationalization of B Corp principles. Another enabler is a core value proposition centered on addressing social and environmental problems through the organization's offerings along with an organizational philosophy grounded in ethical principles and moral standards such as empathy, advocacy, awareness, sharing, and collaboration [52].</p>
<p>Regenerative Business Model</p>	<p>A Regenerative Business Model (RBM) is a business model that creates, delivers, and captures value by embedding planetary health, societal wellbeing, and ecological regeneration as core business objectives [7, 61]. RBMs go beyond SBMs by fundamentally reorienting business logic toward delivering net positive outcomes for nature and society, rather than merely minimizing harm or optimizing resource efficiency, and by considering the environment as their key stakeholder [11].</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The main goal of an RBM is to contribute to planetary health and societal wellbeing by delivering net positive value across multiple and all stakeholder levels, including nature, society, customers, suppliers, partners, shareholders, investors, and employees [7, 11, 61]. RBMs aspire to give back more than they utilize and to support the regeneration of ecological and social systems, rather than just seeking to mitigate harm [61]. This reflects a shift from minimizing negative impacts to enhancing the wellbeing of society and the planet through business activity.</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> RBMs operationalize their goals by promoting regenerative leadership and fostering co-creative partnerships with nature, grounded in principles of justice and fairness [7]. Central to their operation is the prioritization of planetary health and societal wellbeing within decision-making processes. RBMs adopt a multistakeholder approach that positions the planet as a key stakeholder and, as well as integrate a social-ecological systems perspective [11]. Furthermore, RBMs set explicit goals directed towards societal or nature regeneration, ensuring that regeneration is embedded within the strategic orientation of the business [61].</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> RBMs are enabled by the application of multicapital accounting[7, 61], which broadens value measurement beyond financial metrics to account for multiple forms of capital, including natural and social capital. Additionally, they leverage restore-preserve-enhance strategies [11, 61], which comprise regenerative leadership, nature regeneration, social regeneration, responsible sourcing, human health and wellbeing focus, and employee-level initiatives, to support their implementation. The value proposition of RBMs explicitly links planetary health and societal wellbeing to</p>

	the business [7], reinforcing their regenerative intent and providing a tangible foundation for decision-making and stakeholder engagement.
Circular Startup	<p>Circular Start-ups (CS) are early-stage, innovative ventures that adopt and pursue the logic of CBMs from inception [62, 63], but are conceptually distinct from CBMs. Namely, although they operate through a CBM, they are not merely early-stage CBMs, as they combine entrepreneurial novelty with a system-level orientation towards accelerating the transition to a circular economy [63]. Unlike established firms adopting CBMs, CS are able play a pioneering role by shaping the conditions, knowledge, and legitimacy necessary for circular innovations to diffuse within markets and ecosystems [64]. They simultaneously focus on business model innovation, system transformation, and ecosystem engagement from the earliest stages of their development.</p> <p><i>Goals:</i> The main goal of CS is to contribute to the transition towards CE. In doing so, they aim to generate environmental, economic, and social value by decoupling growth from resource consumption, closing material loops, and safeguarding resources for future use [62, 63].</p> <p><i>Mechanisms:</i> CS operationalize their goals by adopting the rationale of and actively pursuing a CBM [62, 63]. This involves the design and implementation of circular economy principles and logic that enables the narrowing, closing, slowing, and regeneration of resource loops. Furthermore, they contribute to creating legitimacy for innovative solutions and forming new knowledge that supports circular economy practices [64].</p> <p><i>Enablers:</i> CS are supported by two key enablers. First, they adopt distinct strategies according to their type, which may be design-based, waste-based, platform-based, service-based, or nature-based, reflecting different pathways through which circularity principles can be operationalized and scaled [63]. Second, they take on specific roles within their ecosystems (conveners, reinforcers, pioneers, and/or champions) [64] which enable them to build networks, mobilize resources, and influence institutional environments conducive to circular innovation and business model diffusion.</p>

Section 3: SOBM Concept Taxonomy

Taxonomy Type Scheme

Dimension	Definition	Characteristic	Definition
D1. Category (mutually exclusive)	The classes of objects that share common characteristics.	D1.1 Business Models	The object “describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers and captures value”[65] for certain stakeholders.
		D1.2 Multi-logic Organizations	The object describes organizations that embody more than one institutional logic at the same time; which are “defined as socially constructed sets of material practices, assumptions, values, and beliefs that shape cognition and behavior (Thornton, Ocasio, & Lounsbury, 2012)”[66]
		D1.3 Start Up	The object describes an early-stage venture that validates a viable path to scale and operates in an environment of limited resources and high uncertainty.
		D1.4 Mechanisms	The object is a mechanism for value creation, delivery or capture.
		D1.5 Innovation Process	The object describes an innovation process towards novel products, services, processes or business models.
		D1.6 Innovation	The object describes an implemented realization of a novel or significantly improved product, service, or process.
		D1.7 Entrepreneurial Approach	The object describes an approach for the exploration and exploitation of opportunities by entrepreneurs.
		D1.8 Economic Paradigm	The object describes a set of macro-level principles describing how an economy should work.
D2. Primary Focus	The <u>core</u> Triple-Bottom-Line sustainability dimension(s) [67] the object aims to affect.	D2.1 Environmental Impact	The object aims to contribute to environmental quality to achieve environmental sustainability.
		D2.2 Social Impact	The object aims to contribute to social justice and capital to achieve social sustainability.
		D2.3 Economic Impact	The object aims to contribute to economic prosperity for the firm and stakeholders to achieve economic sustainability.
D3. Secondary Focus	The <u>ancillary</u> Triple-Bottom-Line sustainability dimension(s) [67] that the object intentionally supports or demonstrably influences, but are not the object’s core aim.	D3.1 Environmental Impact	The object aims to contribute to environmental quality to achieve environmental sustainability.
		D3.2 Social Impact	The object aims to contribute to social justice and capital to achieve social sustainability.
		D3.3 Economic Impact	The object aims to contribute to economic prosperity for the firm and stakeholders to achieve economic sustainability.
D4. Extent of Impact (mutually exclusive)	The direction and magnitude of the targeted impact(s) the objects aim to produce.	D4.1 Net positive	The object aims to create more positive impact and reduce negative impact, resulting in a significant net surplus of positive impact.
		D4.2 Positive	The object aims to compensate the negative impacts it creates with equivalent positive impacts, resulting in a negligible or zero net effect.

Section 4: Evaluation Goals Questionnaire

Please answer after completing the classification. Elaborations should be provided for scores of ≤ 3 *

Evaluation Goal	Question	1* (strongly disagree)	2* (disagree)	3* (neutral)	4 (agree)	5 (strongly agree)
Identifying	I1. The taxonomy provides sufficient detail to uniquely distinguish objects from each other.					
	<i>Elaboration:</i>					
Classifying	C1. The dimension definitions are adequate to classify objects consistently.					
	<i>Elaboration:</i>					
	C2. The characteristic definitions are adequate to classify objects consistently.					
	<i>Elaboration:</i>					
	C3. Ambiguities that arise are due to object definition limitations rather than unclear taxonomy wording.					
<i>Elaboration:</i>						
Analyzing	A1. The set of dimensions and characteristics provide a clear basis to compare the objects (similarities/differences).					
	<i>Elaboration:</i>					
	A2. The taxonomy could support analytical insights beyond mere labeling (e.g., patterns across objects/dimensions). <i>Please elaborate if you score $4 \leq$</i>					
<i>Elaboration:</i>						